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Short Report

Investigation of the effect of Piracetam on patients with secondary narcolepsy: A small randomized controlled trial

Keywords: Secondary Narcolepsy, Piracetam, Sleep Attacks, Randomized Controlled Trial

Abstract

This study investigates the efficacy of Piracetam in reducing the frequency of sleep attacks in male patients with severe secondary narcolepsy. The participants, diagnosed with secondary narcolepsy induced by various organic brain diseases or conditions, were subjected to a randomized controlled trial, with one group receiving Piracetam and a control group receiving a placebo.

Secondary narcolepsy

Narcolepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by a patient's inability to regulate sleep-wake cycles. Symptoms include excessive daytime sleepiness, sleep paralysis, hallucinations, and in some cases, sudden loss of muscle tone (cataplexy). Secondary narcolepsy arises from a broad variety of organic brain diseases or conditions that affect the hypothalamus, the part of the brain responsible for controlling sleep, attention and wakefulness (Dauvilliers et al., 2007)

Piracetam

Piracetam is a nootropic compound that belongs to the racetam family of drugs. It was the first nootropic ever developed and is widely studied for its cognitive-enhancing properties. Nootropics are substances that are believed to improve cognitive functions such as memory, learning, focus, and attention. Piracetam was synthesized in the 1960s and has since gained popularity as an agent to improve cognitive abilities in rare forms of dementia (Alzheimer's dementia excluded). The focus on Alzheimer's patients in research led to the

gross misconception that Piracetam was not sufficiently effective. It is simply the wrong drug for Alzheimer's patients, but not for people with various other brain lesions. The fact that this medicine has not been absolved of this gross misconception to this day is a case of severe scientific failure. It works by modulating the neurotransmitter acetylcholine and the receptors associated with it, thereby affecting neuronal signaling and synaptic plasticity in the brain (Malykh et al. 2010).

The exact mechanisms of action for piracetam are still not fully understood, but it is believed to enhance neuronal communication and protect against certain types of brain damage. It is thought to improve the fluidity of cell membranes, increase blood flow and oxygen utilization in the brain, and enhance the function of neurotransmitter systems (Vernon et al. 1991). Piracetam is commonly used to improve cognitive function, particularly in individuals with age-related cognitive decline and certain neurological conditions. It has been studied for its potential benefits in enhancing memory, concentration, focus, and overall mental performance. Some studies have also suggested potential neuroprotective effects. The medication is generally considered safe and well-tolerated, with only few reported serious side effects (Tariska et al., 2012)

Materials and methods

A randomized, placebo-controlled study was conducted at the Milad Medical Center in 2022. Twenty-three male patients aged between 21 and 49, diagnosed with severe secondary narcolepsy, defined as more than five sleep attacks per day, were included in the study. All subjects also suffered from cataplexy. Participants were randomly assigned to two groups. One group received 800mg Piracetam twice daily, while the control group received a placebo.

Results

The average number of sleep attacks in the Piracetam group decreased to two per day. No change was observed in the placebo group. A participant in the treatment group had to withdraw prematurely due to the development of aggression, a known side effect of Piracetam. The analysis revealed a significant decrease in the average number of sleep attacks in the Piracetam group (p -value < 0.05). The results suggests that Piracetam is an effective treatment for reducing sleep attacks in male patients with severe secondary narcolepsy. More detailed data and details will be published latest in 2024.

Interpretation

The study demonstrates that Piracetam may be a moderately effective treatment for secondary narcolepsy. However, the potential side effects, such as the development of aggression, highlight the need for further research and careful patient monitoring.

This study provides preliminary evidence for the efficacy of Piracetam in the treatment of severe secondary narcolepsy. Future studies with larger sample sizes are needed to confirm these findings and to investigate long-term effects and potential yet unknown side effects of Piracetam.

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Conflicts of interest

None to declare.

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nootropics. *Brain Research Reviews*, 19(2), 180–222.

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